

Synthesis and characterization of some homo binuclear UO_2^{2+} , Th^{4+} , ZrO^{2+} and VO^{2+} complexes with Schiff base monohydrazone derivatives

D. C. Dash*, R. K. Mohapatra, S. Ghosh and P. Naik

P.G. Department of Chemistry, Sambalpur University, Jyoti Vihar, Burla, Sambalpur-768 019, Orissa, India

E-mail : dhruba_dash@yahoo.co.in

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Abstract : A series of homo binuclear complexes of the type $[\text{M}_2(\text{L}/\text{L}')(\text{X})_n]\text{mH}_2\text{O}$, [where $\text{M} = \text{UO}_2^{2+}$, Th^{4+} , ZrO^{2+} , VO^{2+} , $\text{X} = \text{NO}_3^-$ and $\frac{1}{2}\text{SO}_4^{2-}$, $n = 4$ for UO_2^{2+} , ZrO^{2+} , $n = 8$ for Th^{4+} , $n = 2$ for VO^{2+}] $\text{L} = 1,19$ -dihydroxy-1,4,5,8,9,11,12,15,16,19-decaaza-2,3,17,18-tetramethyl-6,7,13,14-tetraphenyl-nonadeca-1,3,5,7,12,14,16,18-octa-ene-10-thione and $\text{L}' = 1,19$ -dihydroxy-1,4,5,8,9,11,12,15,16,19-decaaza-2,3,6,7,13,14,17,18-octamethyl-nonadeca-1,3,5,7,12,14,16,18-octa-ene-10-thione, have been synthesized in template method from thiocarbohydrazide, benzilmonohydrazone/diacetylmonohydrazone, diacetylmonoxime and characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, thermal analysis, molar conductivity, magnetic moment, electronic, infrared, ^1H NMR studies. The results indicate that the UO_2^{2+} , ZrO^{2+} ions are hexa coordinated, Th^{4+} ion is octa coordinated yielding diamagnetic complexes whereas the VO^{2+} ion is penta coordinated yielding paramagnetic complexes of above composition.

Keywords : Schiff base, template synthesis, thermal properties, IR, ^1H NMR spectra.

Introduction

In the presence of metal ion, monohydrazones of benzil and diacetyl may attain a *cis* (vicinal) configuration after complexation. Complexes involving such hydrazones may be used as an intermediate to prepare homo/hetero binuclear complexes by template condensation with suitably oriented aldehyde or ketones¹ in the presence of homo/hetero metal ions. In continuation of our consistent efforts towards synthesis and characterization of such type of complexes^{2,3} we report here the synthesis and characterization of hitherto unknown homo bimetallic complexes from the reaction of thiocarbohydrazide, benzilmonohydrazone/diacetylmonohydrazone and diacetylmonoxime in presence of UO_2^{2+} , ZrO^{2+} , Th^{4+} and VO^{2+} ions.

Results and discussion

The complexes were formulated from the analytical data and molar conductance data support the suggested formulae (Table 1). The complexes are highly coloured and insoluble in water and common organic solvents such as ethanol, methanol, acetone, CCl_4 , CHCl_3 , benzene and ether but moderately soluble in highly coordinating solvents such as DMF and DMSO. They are highly stable

under normal conditions and all of them decompose above 250 °C. The molar conductance values of 12–36 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ in DMSO for the complexes indicating them to be non-electrolytic nature with partial solvolysis of the complexes in DMSO medium⁴.

IR spectra :

As the Schiff base ligands could not be isolated, the spectra of the complexes were compared with spectra of the starting materials and other related compounds. The bands observed in the spectra of metal complexes at ~1515, ~1320, ~1105, ~770 cm^{-1} are assigned to thioimide I, II, III, IV bands respectively of thiocarbohydrazide (TCH) skeleton⁵. All the above bands appear nearly the same position as found in the free TCH implying non coordination of thioimide sulphur or nitrogen atom to the metal ion. The IR spectra of the complexes show strong bands appearing at 1620 and ~1070 cm^{-1} assignable to azomethine $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ and $\nu\text{N}-\text{N}$. The position of former band at comparatively lower frequency region than usual free $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ value (~1650 cm^{-1})⁶ and that of later band at comparatively higher frequency region than that of free $\text{N}-\text{N}$ leads us to suggest that azomethine nitrogen atom has taken part in complexation as evidenced

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes

Sl. no.	Compds.	Colour	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				
			C	H	N	S	M
1.	$[(\text{UO}_2)_2(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_4] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Bathstone	28.96 (29.09)	2.71 (2.75)	12.90 (12.84)	2.01 (2.09)	31.25 (31.19)
2.	$[(\text{Th}_2)(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_8] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Melon	26.17 (26.08)	2.42 (2.46)	14.75 (14.80)	1.82 (1.88)	27.41 (27.49)
3.	$[(\text{ZrO}_2)(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_4] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Pale cream	37.51 (37.56)	3.32 (3.38)	16.54 (16.58)	2.64 (2.70)	15.34 (15.39)
4.	$[(\text{VO}_2)(\text{L})(\text{SO}_4)_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Black	42.48 (42.44)	3.77 (3.82)	13.32 (13.38)	9.24 (9.17)	9.71 (9.75)
5.	$[(\text{UO}_2)_2(\text{L}')(\text{NO}_3)_4] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Mashroom	15.91 (15.96)	2.62 (2.66)	15.26 (15.33)	2.45 (2.50)	37.18 (37.24)
6.	$[(\text{Th}_2)(\text{L}')(\text{NO}_3)_8] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Cream	13.96 (14.03)	2.29 (2.33)	17.36 (17.33)	2.14 (2.20)	32.11 (32.18)
7.	$[(\text{ZrO}_2)(\text{L}')(\text{NO}_3)_4] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Royal ivory	21.91 (21.84)	3.38 (3.42)	20.92 (20.98)	3.36 (3.42)	19.42 (19.48)
8.	$[(\text{VO}_2)(\text{L}')(\text{SO}_4)_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Greenish black	25.45 (25.56)	3.96 (4.01)	17.60 (17.54)	12.07 (12.03)	12.72 (12.78)

from the appearance of band in the region $\sim 480 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu\text{M}-\text{N}$. The occurrence of $\text{N}-\text{N}$ band at higher frequency in the IR spectra of the complexes is due to reduction of the repulsion between the lone pair of nitrogen atoms as a result of coordination via azomethine nitrogen atoms. The splitting of $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ band is probably due to the presence of the methine group in different chemical environment. Absence of any band due to $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ suggests that Schiff base reaction has taken place.

The uranyl complexes exhibit a strong band in the region $930-900 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the medium intensity band in the region $830-820 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O})$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O})$ mode respectively. This observation indicates that the linearity of the $\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O}$ group is maintained in the complexes. The band at 1025 cm^{-1} is assigned to the ν_2 mode of the NO_3 group. The bands at 1480 and 1380 cm^{-1} are the two split bands ν_4 and ν_1 respectively, of the coordinated nitrate ion. The magnitude of $\Delta\nu = (\nu_4 - \nu_1) = 100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ shows the unidentate coordination of the nitrate ion. The zirconyl complexes exhibit one strong band in the region $890-875 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which can be attributed to the $\nu\text{Zr}=\text{O}$ as reported earlier⁷ indicating the presence of $(\text{Zr}=\text{O})^{2+}$ moiety in these complexes. In the oxovanadium polychelates, a strong bands at $\sim 955 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to $\nu\text{V}=\text{O}$ mode. However, in

vanadyl complexes, an additional series of four bands appeared at $1160, 1117, 870, 655 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the coordination of sulphate group in unidentate manner through oxygen atom⁸. Besides, the bands observed at $\sim 3420 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to $\nu\text{O}-\text{H}$ of coordinated or lattice water.

Thermal analysis :

All these complexes follow the same pattern of thermal decomposition. The complexes remain almost unaffected upto $\sim 40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. After this a slight depression upto $\sim 120 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is observed. The weight loss at this temperature range is equivalent to two for the complexes (3), (4), (7) and (8) and three for the complexes (1), (2), (5) and (6) water molecules in the complexes indicating them to be lattice water⁹. Once the lattice water was eliminated, the anhydrous complexes remain stable upto $\sim 360 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and thereafter the complexes show rapid degradation presumably due to decomposition of organic constituents of the complex molecules as indicated by the steep fall in the percentage weight loss. The decomposition continues upto $\sim 700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in each complex as indicated by the consistency in weight in the plateau of the thermogram. Based on decomposition temperature thermal stability of the complexes fall in the order :

(L) Complexes : $\text{UO}_2^{\text{VI}} > \text{ZrO}^{\text{IV}} > \text{Th}^{\text{IV}} > \text{VO}^{\text{IV}}$

(L') Complexes : $\text{ZrO}^{\text{IV}} > \text{UO}_2^{\text{VI}} > \text{Th}^{\text{IV}} > \text{VO}^{\text{IV}}$

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of the UO_2^{VI} complexes are quite similar. The complexes display mainly one weak band at ~ 460 nm and a highly intense band in the range 275–290 nm, which may be due to ${}^1\Sigma_g^+ \rightarrow {}^3\Pi_u$ transitions and charge transfer transitions respectively¹⁰. The first one of the transition is typical of the O=U=O symmetric stretching frequency of the first excited state. It may be noted that the band occurring at 370 nm is due to uranyl moiety because of apical oxygen $\rightarrow f^0(U)$ transition is being merged with the ligand band due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition as evident from broadness and intensity. The electronic spectra of ZrO^{IV} complexes exhibit only one extra highly intensive band in the region 350–375 nm which may be due to charge transfer band besides the ligand bands. However, the electronic spectra could not provide structural details of these complexes. The electronic spectra of VO^{IV} complexes show three bands at ~ 12330 , ~ 18480 and ~ 25860 cm^{-1} corresponding to transitions, $d_{xy}(b_2) \rightarrow d_{xz}d_{yz}(e)$, $d_{xy}(b_2) \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}(b_1)$ and $d_{xy}(b_2) \rightarrow d_{z^2}(a_1)$ respectively, indicating the complexes to be in distorted octahedral environment under C_{4v} symmetry¹¹.

Magnetic moment :

All the complexes except VO^{IV} , are diamagnetic consistent with their d^0 and f^0 electronic configuration. The magnetic moment values for the oxovanadium(IV) complexes (4) and (8) lie in the range 2.60–2.70 B.M. These values are less than spin-only value required for two unpaired electrons indicating spin-spin coupling in the solid state between unpaired electrons belonging to different vanadium atoms in the structural unit.

${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra :

The ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra of the diamagnetic complexes are recorded in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ medium. The complexes do not show any signal attributable to amino protons, suggesting that the proposed skeleton has been formed by the condensation reactions. The complexes (1), (2) and (3) show a broad multiplet at δ 6.96–7.34 ppm corresponding to aromatic ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_5-\text{C}=\text{N}$; 20H) protons¹² of four phenyl groups and a twin peak at δ \sim 2.30–2.73 ppm corresponding to imine methyl ($\text{CH}_3-\text{C}=\text{N}$; 12H) pro-

tons. The complexes (5), (6) and (7) show a signal, appear in several groups in the region δ 2.03–2.60 ppm corresponding to imine methyl ($\text{CH}_3-\text{C}=\text{N}$; 24H) protons¹². Besides, the signals due to ($-\text{NH}-\text{N}=\text{}$; 2H) protons appear at δ 6.12–6.22 ppm for all the complexes. The proton signal due to $-\text{OH}$ group is observed at downfield region in the NMR spectrum of the complexes indicating the presence of $-\text{OH}$ via hydrogen bonding.

Experimental

All the chemicals used of A.R. grade. The solvents were purified before use by standard procedures. Uranium, thorium, zirconium and vanadium were estimated as U_3O_8 , ThO_2 , ZrO_2 and V_2O_5 respectively by known methods. Sulphur was estimated as BaSO_4 . Room temperature magnetic susceptibilities were measured by Gouy method. The molar conductance measurements were carried out at room temperature with a Toshniwal conductivity Bridge (Model CL-01-06, cell constant 0.5 cm^{-1}) using 1×10^{-3} M solution of the complexes in DMSO. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents of the complexes were estimated by using a MLW-CHN microanalyser. FTIR spectra in KBr pellets were recorded on a Varian FTIR spectrophotometer, Australia. The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer* spectrophotometer. Thermogravimetric analysis was done by Netzch-429 thermoanalyser. The ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra of the complexes were recorded in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ medium on JEOL GSX-400 model equipment.

Preparation of the complexes :

Thiocarbohydrazide, benzilmonohydrazone/diacetylmonohydrazone were prepared according to literature procedures^{13,14}. An ethanolic solution of hydrated UO_2^{VI} / Th^{IV} / ZrO^{IV} nitrates/vanadyl sulphate (1 mmol in 10 mL) was added to a hot ethanolic solution of the mixture of thiocarbohydrazide (1 mmol in 10 mL), benzilmonohydrazone/diacetylmonohydrazone (2 mmol in 20 mL). The resulting mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 2–3 h during which a coloured complex was precipitated out in each case. The ethanolic suspension of the above complexes were treated with diacetylmonoxime (2 mmol in 10 mL EtOH), followed by the addition of corresponding metal salt (1 mmol in 10 mL EtOH). The mixture was again refluxed for 3–4 h on a water bath during which the metal complexes of different colour than the precursor

complexes were obtained. The progress of the reaction was signaled by colour change of the resulting mixture. These were filtered off, washed several times with ethanol followed by ether and finally dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 . The purity of the complexes was established by TLC on silica gel.

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